

Increasing Cervical Cancer Screening Participation in Veterans

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Background

- Approximately 280,000 deaths are linked to cervical cancer in developed countries
- Service members have a lower rate of cervical cancer screening (CCS) and a higher incidence of HPV cervical dysplasia compared to the general population

Recommendation in Evidence

- Increase the rate of CCS, inclusive of Papanicolaou (Pap) smear and hrHPV testing for early detection

Problem

At a VHA Medical Facility in Southern California in March 2023, the CCS completion rate was 65.91%, while the national benchmark is 81%

Purpose

To increase CCS rates by 10% in veteran patients aged 21-65 by providing 1:1 patient education on cervical cancer screening and utilize an evidence-based tool to collect patient perceived barriers to completing CCS

Methods

Framework: Logic Model

Setting

- Level 1a VHA Medical Facility in So CA
- Approximately 50,000 veterans served at the medical center and 7 satellite campuses

Sample

- 39 CCS overdue veterans, available to clinician's phone contact during the implementation period

Intervention: 1:1 Phone Contact

- Patient education on CCS using a script
- Survey on perceived barriers utilizing 9 questions adapted from CPC-28 questionnaire

Intervention Period: 10/14/2024 -11/14/2024

Data Collection

CCS Education Completion Rate

- Number of veterans who received CCS education

CCS Perceived Barriers

- Number of veterans who participated in CCS barrier survey
- Perceived barriers to complete CCS

CCS Completion Rates

- Number of veterans who completed CCS
- Organization's quarterly report on CCS completion rate

Data Analysis: Descriptive Statistics

Results

CCS Education Completion Rate

- 37 Veterans out of 39 contacted agreed to receive CCS education (37/39 = 94.9%)

CCS Perceived Barriers

- 12 out of 37 educated veterans participated in barrier survey (12/37 = 32.4%)
- Reported barriers: A2 (n=1), A3 (n=3), A4 (n=1), A10 (n=2), A11 (n=1)

#	Text "I have not taken a Pap test...because"	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
A2	I do not have time to get a Pap test	0	1	0	0
A3	they treat me badly in the health care center	0	3	0	0
A4	I do not know at what age it is necessary to have a Pap test	0	1	0	0
A5	when I go, I need to wait a long time to be seen	0	0	0	0
A7	I am afraid to find out if I have cancer	0	0	0	0
A8	the health care center is only open during hours when I cannot go	0	0	0	0
A9	I am embarrassed to have a genital exam	0	0	0	0
A10	I do not know how often I need to get a Pap test	0	2	0	0
A11	it is difficult to get an appointment	0	1	0	0

CCS Completion Rate

- 6 out of 37 who received CCS education completed CCS as intervened (6/37 = 16.2%)
- Organizational quarterly report indicated of increased CCS rate 65.91% to 74.9%

Timeframe	%CCS Completions	
FY23Q2	65.91%	Baseline
FY24Q1	74.9%	Post-Intervention
FY24 YTD	74.9%	As of Jan 10, 2024

Discussion

- 94.9% contacted veterans accepted CCS education, indicating openness to 1:1 education offered by clinician
- 32.4% veterans received CCS education agreed to share their barriers to CCS, highlighting the need of alternative tools
- Tailored strategies are essential to address each identified barrier effectively
- 16.2% veterans received CCS education completed CCS within 8-week intervention period, surpassing the project goal of 10%
- CCS rate increased to 9%, close to 10% project goal

Dissemination to Organization's Leadership and Stakeholders

- Presented project outcomes to leaders
- Addressed individual perceived barriers and corresponding strategies
- Explored both provider-specific and organizational barriers, along with methods for improvement

Limitations

- Single site intervention
- Small sample size
- Sampling bias
- Membership bias

Recommendations

- Interdepartmental collaboration with mental health
- Further study on the relationship between mental illness and/or SUD and CCS completion in veterans

References

